

Sustainable Facilities Management in Novo Nordisk

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INTRODUCTION

Facilities management (FM) is found in all organizations, large as well as small. The activities within FM are widespread and have, in many ways, impacts on environment as well as climate every day. It is therefore relevant to work out a framework for companies to use in order for them to analyze the company's FM activities and find ways of improving the sustainability in these activities.

THEORY

The theory used in this case is mainly regular FM theory and sustainability theory with main focus on environmental and climate impacts.

However, also theories about companies' corporate social responsibilities (CSR) are supposed to play a part in the final framework.

METHOD

In the specific case with Novo Nordisk information about the company's FM and sustainability profile was collected through the Internet, followed by semi-structured interviews with people within the relevant areas.

The interview were made in the three organizational levels, operational, tactical and strategic, to create a complete picture of the understanding of sustainable FM throughout the organization.

At the operational level the research is focused on the realization strategies and barriers/possibilities in FM processes including suggestions for innovation and sustainable improvements.

At the tactical level the research is related to the role the FM department plays in relation to the sustainable profile of the organization. Also the relations to the HR department and whether or not the department is pro- or reactive when it comes to sustainability are being investigated.

At the strategic level attention is on the overall sustainability strategy for the organization, followed by analysis of how this corresponds to the FM practices.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Since the project and research is still ongoing, there is yet no results and conclusions. However, the general impression is that not much of the organization's sustainability profile is related to the FM activities, and that there therefore are lots of possibilities for suggestions for sustainable improvements in the department.